

Stress Management on Factors Affecting the Frontline Hospitality Employees in City of Dreams Hotel, Manila

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Abstract: Stress creates a negative reaction to situations happening in an environment. Identifying the factors that triggers stress helps in creating a solution in which stress can be properly handled by individuals at any given time. Development of stress management program is formulated by identifying the different stressors in which the respondents has given the researchers. Front of the house hospitality employees often encounters stress triggers due to various factors. Insufficiency of research on identifying the different stress factors on frontline hospitality employees necessitate the direction of this research. This paper analyzed responses of the front of the house hospitality employees of the City of Dream Hotel in Manila regarding the different stress factors that the respondents encounter to formulate a stress management program. Furthermore, this study made use of a researcher-made online questionnaire which was administered to 50 respondents in different departments that encounters hotel guests face to face. The results showcase that the respondents have variety of factors triggering stress affecting the respondents. This implies that the stress management program created to tackle the different problems, is to create positive reinforcement to the different factors that triggers stress to the respondents.

Keywords: Stress Management, Factors of Stress, Front of the house Hospitality.

I. INTRODUCTION

Stress is physical and physiological reaction to a surrounding, and it is caused by events in the workplace. (Hameed, 2019; Luqman, 2019; Rasheed, 2019; Yousaf, 2019). This shows that stress is a serious problem especially in a working environment that pulls the quality of the work force down. (Jaganath, 2019). Stress causes friction at work that is often unreasoned well that comes when employees' expectations aren't met with the company's, which disconnects them, it is detrimental to morale that leads do poor productivity. (Rappler, 2016). Occupational stress has a negative effect when it comes on providing customer service and satisfaction. (Akgunduz, 2015). One of the important. Every work force can be stressed with various factors that pulls the quality of work from high to low which translates to poor service. (Goel, 2017; Rao, 2017). Strong mental health can overcome negative effects of stress to different situations. (Jung, 2016; Yoon, 2016).

People can easily feel and conclude that they are stress. Every people encounter different problems and struggles that can be their stressors. But stress is a natural reaction to life experiences. From our everyday situations from work, family, love, and even to ourselves can trigger stress. Stress is physical and physiological reaction to a surrounding, and it is caused by events in the workplace. The person can feel headaches, fatigue, indigestion, ulcers, strokes, and heart attacks. (Hameed, 2019; Luqman, 2019; Rasheed, 2019; Yousaf, 2019).

Stress is a psychological reaction to threatening situation in an environment that causes distress in person's health. When a person reaches its maximum capacity, it brings negative actions such as anger, frustration, bad actions, and even blame other people. This shows that stress is a serious problem especially in a working environment that pulls the quality of the work force down. A survey made by Statistics Canada in 2018 revealed that employees become stressful due to lack of career opportunities, heavy workload, and long working hours which reveals that one in four Canadians leaves their job due to stress. Moving further, the survey revealed that 30% of employees that are ages 35 to 40 are extremely stressful. (Jaganath, 2019). In Manila, work is always accompanied with stress. Some causes of stress are friction at work that is often unreasoned well that comes when employees' expectations aren't met with the companies. This leads to mismatch of personal and company policies and also creates distance from employer to employee which disconnects them, it is detrimental to morale that leads do poor productivity. (Rappler, 2016). The industry of Hospitality which is also known for its non-stop working system is also at the edge of encountering stress in workplace environment. In Hospitality Industry, stress is one of the main factors that can affect personnel's workplace performance at all costs. Occupational stress has a negative effect when it comes on providing customer service and satisfaction. The workplace has been stated as one of the biggest factors that can decrease the productivity of the employees in an organization during many years. (Akgunduz, 2015).

The hospitality industry operates with a very important component which are hotels that serves tourists with comfortable and secure place to stay. Hotels are being rated by tourists based on their quality or service and facilities. One of the important factors that plays a big role in a hotel is the work force that satisfy the needs of every guest. Every work force can be stressed with various factors that pulls the quality of work from high to low which translates to poor service. (Goel, 2017; Rao, 2017). Having healthy employees that has emotional intelligence indicates that coping up with stress shows positive outcomes for the betterment of the company. This study indicates that emotional intelligence can increase job satisfaction and better working performance under stress. With EL, employees can maximize their capability to perform on great pressure. Strong mental health can overcome negative effects of stress to different situations. (Jung, 2016; Yoon, 2016).

Role ambiguity, role conflict, and job overload creates stress to employees that makes it a great concern regarding poor performance thus create negative impact on the company. It was discovered that role ambiguity triggers stress to employees with the addition of role conflict and work overload. It simply makes challenges that weighs down the employee's capability to perform well in the work environment. Boosting the employee's self-esteem can help in increasing job performance which overcomes the stress made by factors in the workplace. (Akgunduz, 2015).

Book IV – Health, Safety and Social Welfare Benefits by The Department of Labor and Employment

CHAPTER I

MEDICAL AND DENTAL SERVICES

Art. 159. Health program. The physician engaged by an employer shall, in addition to his duties under this Chapter, develop and implement a comprehensive occupational health program for the benefit of the employees of his employer.

Art. 160. Qualifications of health personnel. The physicians, dentists and nurses employed by employers pursuant to this Chapter shall have the necessary training in industrial medicine and occupational safety and health. The Secretary of Labor and Employment, in consultation with industrial, medical, and occupational safety and health associations, shall establish the qualifications, criteria and conditions of employment of such health personnel.

Art. 161. Assistance of employer. It shall be the duty of any employer to provide all the necessary assistance to ensure the adequate and immediate medical and dental attendance and treatment to an injured or sick employee in case of emergency.

CHAPTER II

OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH AND SAFETY

Art. 162. Safety and health standards. The Secretary of Labour and Employment shall, by appropriate orders, set and enforce mandatory occupational safety and health standards to eliminate or reduce occupational safety and health hazards in all workplaces and institute new, and update existing, programs to ensure safe and healthful working conditions in all places of employment.

Art. 165. Administration of safety and health laws.

The Department of Labour and Employment shall be solely responsible for the administration and enforcement of occupational safety and health laws, regulations and standards in all establishments and workplaces wherever they may be located; however, chartered cities may be allowed to conduct industrial safety inspections of establishments within their respective jurisdictions where they have adequate facilities and competent personnel for the purpose as determined by the Department of Labour and Employment and subject to national standards established by the latter.

The Secretary of Labour and Employment may, through appropriate regulations, collect reasonable fees for the inspection of steam boilers, pressure vessels and piping and electrical installations, the test and approval for safe use of materials, equipment and other safety devices and the approval of plans for such materials, equipment and devices. The fee so collected shall be deposited in the national treasury to the credit of the occupational safety and health fund and shall be expended exclusively for the administration and enforcement of safety and other labour laws administered by the Department of Labour and Employment.

The City of Dreams Hotel is one of the world class hotels. City of Dreams is an outstanding hotel that will serve as a great source of information that will help the study in producing a quality and effective stress management program for the front of the house employees in the hospitality industry.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The researchers want to study the City of Dreams employees in Manila. The researchers aim to create proper handling to the possible stressors that the employees have and how they can turn it into positive. This study indicates that stress management can increase job satisfaction and better working performance under stress. Without providing and studying stress management employees will continue to show poor performance while in the work environment. The study aims to provide an effective and proficient stress management program to the frontline hotel employees that encounters the guests physically.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This study aims to identify the different triggers of stress and the relationship of work stress to the employees for the development of a stress management program.

- [1.] What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - [1.1] Age
 - [1.2] Gender
 - [1.3] Number of years working
 - [1.4] Average monthly salary
 - [1.5] Civil Status
 - [1.6] Employment Status
 - [1.7] Job Position
 - [1.8] Proximity of Residence
- [2.] How do the respondents assess their stress in terms of the following?
 - [2.1] Salary
 - [2.2] Workload
 - [2.3] Customer-employee relationship
 - [2.4] Supervisor relationship
 - [2.5] Hard Deadlines
 - [2.6] Environment
 - [2.7] Lack of support
- [3.] What stress management program can be developed based on the findings of the study?

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Person-environment fit theory states that work-related stress arises because of lack of individual skill, resources, abilities, and the demand in a work environment. When occupational stress occurs, there is an interaction between objective reality and subjective perception, which leads to disappointment and stress to the individual. During a psychological distress, the tendency of an employee to exhibit poor service rises. The different stress factors cause bad quality of service in a work environment. For this study, the researchers will use this as a reference to identify the impact of different factors that triggers stress and determine if the respondents of this study experience these factors in their job that affects their performance. (Pezaro,2018)

RESEARCH PARADIGM

Fig.1 Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 shows the conceptual framework that the researchers used as guide to determine the different variables needed in conducting this study. Using the Input Output Process (IPO) model the Input is composed of the following variables 1. Demographic Profile of Respondents and 2. Factors that triggers stress to the respondents. For the process data gathering through Survey Questionnaire will be conducted and based on the findings stress management program for front of the house employees will be developed as the research Output.

STATEMENT OF HYPOTHESIS

Based on the research problems, is there any significant difference in the various factors of stress that affects the (front of the house employees) respondents?

3. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Stress in the hospitality industry can modify the employee's ability to perform tasks in the workplace. Occupational stress has been revealed as a strong factor that contributes to negative outcomes in workplaces for employees and organizations during the past few decades. The outcomes of occupational stress include, but not limited to, reduced work output, increased accidents, absenteeism, turnover, poor performance and high work-family conflicts. (Hameed, 2019; Luqman, 2019; Rasheed, 2019; Yousaf, 2019).

Hospitality industry is a huge smile factory. However, Job stress delays task productivity in the hospitality industry stress has been one of the most important factors that affect the performance at all the levels, starting from front-line employees to the top management. Job stress in hospitality industry lessens employees' well-being by creating long term exhaustion, which negatively affects service delivery. Occupational stress has a negative influence on providing quality customer service due to the increased exhaustion of the workers. The studies made in the past related to occupational stress in hospitality industry revealed that employees exhibit high stress working in this industry. While this has been the case, the hospitality industry has a disadvantage as it costs billions of dollars for lost productivity and accounts for high absenteeism and sickness. (Jaganath, 2019)

The complex and ever-changing environment of the hotel industry generates an never-ending array of stimuli, pressure, oppression, and demands which can lead to job stress of hotel employees. The nature of work within hotels include, hard deadlines, unexpected interactions with guests, long working hours, night and evening work, repetitive work, high

emotional demands, low influence (control), shift work, high work space and problems with coordination of work. Researchers have identified different elements which can cause occupational stress among hospitality industry employees. Fatigue is a result of working long hours, unpredictable shifts, few breaks, heavy physical demands (manual handling heavy loads, etc.) and mental and emotional demands as stressors in the hospitality industry. Low pay is also a concern since work is remunerated on the basis of proficient standards which tend to be set lower in relation to other services like nursing and policing. Lack of support from supervisors and co-workers has also been evaluated as a factor that cause stress to hotel employees. It becomes more unpleasant when combined with high demand and low control of work. Employees having frequent face to face and voice to voice interactions with customers play a pivotal role in delivering service and establishing strong relationship with customers. Therefore, it is important to retain a pool of motivated, satisfied and committed employees for delivery of service quality and effective resolutions of customer complaints. (Goel, 2019; Rao, 2019).

Business life has numerous sources of stress. Using the Conservation of Resources Theory, it is possible to describe job stress as stress that employees experience in the workplace environment. According to this theory, employees experience stress when:

- They are faced with the danger of losing resources;
- They lose their resources; or
- They are unable to achieve the expected results despite the fact that the resources are available to use

As a separate point, apart from the factors relating to business and organization, such as the policies and the structure of the organization, working conditions and interpersonal relations, the quality of the work done, and work problems that the employees bring home on top of family responsibilities/problems also have an impact on job stress. (Akgunduz, 2015).

The competitiveness of a business is affected by the organizational passion, sense of responsibility and reliability of talented employees, as well as their intellectual properties. Organizations utilize passion and reliability as criteria for the selection of workers in addition to their ability to perform the cognitive aspect. Businesses pay attention to creative and autonomous talented persons who can flexibly perform their duties. This means that the ability to smoothly perform duties together with colleagues and handle one's own emotions has become important not only for individuals' lives but also for success in organizations. Because even talented persons with excellent intellectual capabilities hinder a business' long-term growth if they have little devotion and loyalty. (Jung, 2019; Yoon, 2019)

4. METHODOLOGY

The study uses quantitative method in order to obtain the statistical information gathered from the frontline employees of City of Dreams Manila. The information will focus on different ways of controlling stress and the different effects of stress to the quality of service provided in the hotel. The data gathered will be used in completing the study.

Hospitality industry is a large organization where personnel and employees delivers service through interacting with clients. Can stress really affect and transform the way employees give service? This Study tackles about how stress and mental concerns can deform a hotel's pathway to progress and what are the things that hospitality employees should consider in order to prevent work related stress and job burnout. The topic STRESS MANAGEMENT OF HOSPITALITY EMPLOYEES aims to perform concrete research that can allow hospitality people to understand the mental concerns that can happen inside the workplace which can cause poor performance and delay of tasks.

The researchers' main target and objective is to gather and understand the hotel employee's stress and contribute by means of providing concrete and helpful solution. The City of Dreams Manila is the chosen hotel to do research with; because the area of The City of Dreams is appropriate to the location of the researchers. And the Hotel is one of the finest hotels globally. According to the researchers they want to tackle the 'causes' of these work-related stress. They targeted the hotel front liners who usually face guests and clients. Lastly, they also want to find out how stress can affect one's performance and how they can apply the strategy of stress management in certain situations in order to have a pleasant, composed and productive workplace.

RESEARCH DESIGN

The study will execute quantitative research in order to gather statistical information that is appropriate to the study. The chosen research design will perform a helpful function that will and can support the study.

RESEARCH LOCALE

The study will happen in one of the outstanding 5-star hotel in Manila, which will be the City of Dreams Manila.

PARTICIPANTS OF THE STUDY & RESEARCH SAMPLING

The participants of the study are total of 100 respondents, 20 each from the given department of the researchers which are; front desk, concierge, waiter, bell boy and door man. For the sampling, the researchers will use the stratified random sampling, as the sampling can arrange the collected data, the information and the answer from participants can narrow down.

RESEARCH INSTRUMENT & DATA GATHERING PROCEDURE

In this study, the researchers will use questionnaire survey as their mode of the instrument wherein the questionnaire is cut into two (2) parts, the first part is about the demographic profile of the respondents and the second part will mainly focus on the stressors of the frontline employee (salary, workload, customer relationship, supervisor relationship, hard deadlines, environment & lack of support) in the said locale. For the data gathering procedure, the researchers will seek approval of the candidate respondents, next the researchers will send a link of the survey using different social media platforms such as Facebook, Google Forms, and or Messenger which is accessible and easier to use. Lastly, the survey will take approximately 3-5 minutes.

DATA TREATMENT & ANALYSIS

The data shall be interpreted through descriptive statistics. The researchers will use the following to provide an organized analysis of the results: percentage, weighted mean, and Likert scale. The percentage is determined by partitioning the frequencies of responses against the complete number of responses and have it multiplied by 100. Moreover, the weighted mean is calculated through multiplying the value of the group by the appropriate weight factors and it shall be divided by the complete number of respondents. The researchers will also use the N-way ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) as they have four (4) independent variables (salary, workload, customer relationship, co-workers) to know what the possible stressors of the employees in City of Dreams Manila are.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The research on the stress management of front-line hotel employees at City of Dreams, Manila, is analyzed and interpreted in this part using a quantitative technique. These respondents' answers, which were acquired via the survey method, make up the material of this chapter. Respondents successfully covered the list of questions during interviews.

1. Demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:

Table 1.1 Age

Age	Frequency	Percent
Valid 30-40 years old	19	38.0
41-50 years old	7	14.0
51 and above	4	8.0
Below 30 years old	20	40.0
Total	50	100.0

As shown is the table 1.1, 20 respondents (40%) are aging below 30 years, followed by 38% with 19 respondents for 30-40 years old; 7 responses (14%) aging 41-50, and 8% or 4 respondents answered 51 and above. This result shows that out of 50 respondents, 20 of them or 40% are aging 30 years below.

Table 1.2 Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Valid Female	27	54.0
Male	23	46.0
Total	50	100.0

This table shows that 27 (54%) of the respondents out of 50 (100%), are female. While 23 of them (46%) are male. Which technically conclude that there are more female respondents in the front line of City of Dreams who answered the survey.

Table 1.3 Number of working years

	Frequency	Percent
Valid 11-15 years	5	10.0
5-10 years	14	28.0
Above 15 years	5	10.0
Less than 5 years	26	52.0
Total	50	100.0

As seen in the table 1.3, 26 respondents (52%) work less than 5 years now, followed by 28% with 14 employees who answered 5-10 years, and an equal 10% for employees who works 11-15 and above 15 years. This generally means that out of 50, Most of the employees are working not more than 5 years until present (2022).

Table 1.4 Average Monthly Salary

	Frequency	Percent
Valid 10,000 - 20,000	19	38.0
21,000 - 30,000	19	38.0
Above 30,000	11	22.0
Less than 10,000	1	2.0
Total	50	100.0

Table 1.4 shows that 38% or 19 respondents out of 50 answered 10,000 – 20,000 monthly Salary. Same goes with another 38% of respondents answered 21,000 – 30, 000. Only 11 employees have an average of above 30,000 monthly salary and only 2% (1 response) on the less than 10, 000.

The total of 76% of respondents have a salary averaging 10,000 – 30,000 followed by the 22% of 30,000 salary beneficiaries, while only 1 in 50 answered less than 10,000.

Table 1.5 Civil Status

	Frequency	Percent
Valid Married	30	60.0
Single	20	40.0
Total	50	100.0

As shown in the Table 1.5, 30 employees (60%) are already married while the remaining 40% (20 respondents) responded Single. This presents that most of the employees in the front line of City of Dreams, manila are already married. According to Akgunduz, 2015, The quality of the work completed and work difficulties that employees bring home on top of family responsibilities/problems have an influence on job stress in addition to business and organization-related elements like policies and organizational structure.

Table 1.6 Employment Status

	Frequency	Percent
Valid Full-time	32	64.0
Part-time	18	36.0
Total	50	100.0

This table presents the results on the Employment status of the 50 respondents.

64% (32 employees) are working as a full-time employee in the hotel while the remaining 36% (18 employees) are working as a part timer; for a total of 50 employees (100%).

Table 1.7 Job Position

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Bell boy	10	20.0
	Concierge	10	20.0
	Doorman	10	20.0
	Front desk	10	20.0
	Waiter	10	20.0
	Total	50	100.0

As Shown in the table, it presents the results on the Job Position of the Front-line employees of City of Dreams, Manila. All respondents and their responses are perfectly equal. Each job position choices got 20% of responses as shown in the table (bellboy, concierge, doorman, front desk, and waiter. for a total of 100%.

According to Akgunduz, 2015, With role conflict and workload strain added, it has been found that role ambiguity stresses out employees. Simply put, it creates obstacles that limit an employee's capacity to function effectively in the workplace.

Table 1.8 Proximity of residence

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Outside the city	20	40.0
	Within the city	30	60.0
	Total	50	100.0

The table shows that 60% of the employees (30 respondents) have responded that they are living within Manila, while the remaining 40% of the employees (20 respondents) said that they live outside Manila.

This result concludes that there are more employees who just live within Manila compared to other 40% who might have a trouble in terms of transportation.

2. Respondents Assessment on their stress in terms of:

2.1 Salary

	Mean	Std.dev	rank	interpretation
Q. 1	3.34	0.72	4	agree
Q. 2	3.46	0.65	1.5	agree
Q. 3	3.30	0.58	5	agree
Q.4	3.46	0.68	1.5	agree
Q.5	3.36	0.78	3	agree
Overall mean	3.38	0.42		high

This table presents the respondents' assessment on the salary. The table shows that the respondents strongly agrees that budgeting (Question 2) and salary increase (Question 4) are the factors that stresses them most in terms of salary with an accumulation mean of 3.36 and with a verbal interpretation of Strongly Agree.

According to Rapper 2016, Workplace conflict that frequently goes unaddressed and results from employees' expectations not being met by the employer is one of the factors that contributes to stress. It also causes a gap between the employer and the employee, which is bad for morale and results in poor productivity. This results in a misalignment between personal and corporate policies. Goel, 2019; Rao, 2019 also stated that Low pay is an issue since remuneration is based on proficiency criteria, which are typically lower than those for other services like nursing and law enforcement.

2.2 Workload

	Mean	Std.dev	rank	interpretation
Q.1	3.38	0.64	1	agree
Q.2	3.14	0.73	5	agree
Q.3	3.20	0.70	3	agree
Q.4	3.30	0.74	2	agree
Q.5	3.18	0.80	4	agree
Overall mean	3.24	0.50		high

Table 2.2 shows that most of the respondents agree that too much work (Question 1) Highly contributes to their stress in terms of workload factor. With an accumulated mean of 3.38 and with a verbal interpretation of Strongly Agree. According to Goel, 2019; Rao, 2019, Numerous factors that might lead to occupational stress in those working in the hospitality business have been discovered by researchers. Working long hours, erratic shifts, infrequent breaks, intense physical demands (manually moving large loads, etc.), and hard mental and emotional demands—all of which are stresses in the hospitality industry—lead to fatigue.

2.3 Customer-Employee Relationship

	Mean	Std.dev	rank	interpretation
Q.11	3.28	0.64	2	agree
Q.12	3.00	0.70	5	agree
Q.13	3.02	0.71	4	agree
Q.14	3.26	0.83	3	agree
Q.15	3.30	0.71	1	agree
Overall mean	3.17	0.50		high

In Table 2.3 Customer-Employee Relationship, Q 15 have the highest rank of all which is our respondents are getting more stressed whenever a guest asks for too many amenities or freebies. The least chosen among the five question is Q12, it means that employees of City of Dreams, Manila doesn't feel that stressed when the guest that they accommodate is not that demanding.

2.4 Supervisor Relationship

	Mean	Std.dev	rank	interpretation
Q.16	3.48	0.54	1	agree
Q.17	3.06	0.71	5	agree
Q.18	3.08	0.63	4	agree
Q.19	3.34	0.69	2	agree
Q.20	3.14	0.73	3	agree
Overall mean	3.22	0.42		high

In Table 2.4 Supervisor Relationship, Q17 has the higher rank among the five questions that the researchers gave. The respondents feel more stressed whenever their supervisor is asking for their help since they become conscious about the work that they are doing since the supervisor is looking, they are afraid to hear negative things about how they work.

2.5 Hard Deadlines

	Mean	Std.dev	rank	interpretation
Q.21	3.48	0.58	1	agree
Q.22	3.08	0.78	4	agree
Q.23	3.96	0.78	5	agree
Q.24	3.26	0.72	3	agree
Q.25	3.28	0.78	2	agree
Overall mean	3.21	0.51		high

In Table 2.5 Hard Deadlines, Q21, the employees of the chosen hotel get more stressed when there is a sudden change about the deadlines that they have. Rappler, 2016, stated that some causes of stress are friction from work that is often unreasoned well that comes when the employees' outlooks aren't met with the company expectation. This is one of the reasons that can lead to mismatch of individual expectancy and the company policies that also created a detachment from the employer to the employee that disconnects them, it is unfavorable to morale that leads to deprived efficiency.

2.6 Environment

	Mean	Std.dev	rank	interpretation
Q.26	3.44	0.61	1	agree
Q.27	3.10	0.79	5	agree
Q.28	3.16	0.71	3	agree
Q.29	3.22	0.89	2	agree
Q.30	3.12	0.85	4	agree
Overall mean	3.21	0.52		high

In table 2.7, Q26 has the highest vote, it means that the employees get more stressed when working inside the over-competitive environment. According to Hameed, 2019; Luqman, 2019; Rasheed, 2019; Yousaf, 2019, they stated that the stress is a physical and physiological reaction to a surrounding, and it is caused by the events inside their workplace. They also said that because of the stress because of work, the person can feel headaches, fatigue, indigestion, ulcers, strokes or even heart attacks. It means that when an employee can feel that they are not enjoying and what they get is just stress inside their workplace, a person can experience all those symptoms.

According to Akgunduz, 2015, the hospitality industry is also known as non-stop working system, it is also at the control of confronting anxiety in workplace environment. Inside the industry, the stress is one of the main factors that can affect personnel's workplace performance at all costs.

2.7 Lack of Support

	Mean	Std.dev	rank	interpretation
Q.31	3.34	0.75	1	agree
Q.32	3.22	0.79	2	agree
Q.33	3.14	0.76	3	agree
Q.34	3.10	0.76	4	agree
Q.35	3.04	0.86	5	agree
Overall mean	3.17	0.55		high

As stated in the Table 2.8, Q31 has the highest vote amongst the five choices. The employee gets more stress when they have a lot of things to do by their own, without the guide or help of their supervisors. The least vote amongst the question is Q35, employees of City of Dreams, Manila doesn't feel that much stress when they need to do work at home after doing a lot of things inside their workplace.

6. OUTPUT (STRESS MANAGEMENT PROGRAM)

There is more than one way to alleviate or reduce stress, however, it does not mean every strategy would work. Just like the stressors, employees experience differing kinds and levels of stress.

The first step:

The first step in this stress management program is to identify which type of stress you are currently experiencing. There are many stressors and many different names for those stressors, in this program we will follow Albrecht's 4 types of stress. According to Dr Karl Albrecht in his book stress and the manager, he was able to identify the foundations of stressors. Namely time, anticipatory, situational and encounter stress.

Time stress – any stress that is time-related, it could be a large volume of work in a brief time span which can lead to feelings of pressure, anxiety, or the feeling of not being able to perform well. This stressor can be defined in one word which is deadlines.

Anticipatory stress – is stress coming from a future event or activity, it is the stress we feel when we are about to undergo something outside our comfort zone. It could be stress coming from an upcoming performance review or an upcoming presentation.

Situational stress – this type of stress occurs when a negative situation such an emergency arises. It means a certain situation would trigger stress. It is often caused by situations where we have little to no control over.

Encounter stress – this type of stress happens when there is stress coming from interacting with a person or a group. This stress can lead to avoidance of coworkers or supervisors which in turn can affect work performance.

The second step in this stress management program is to choose which type of coping mechanism best fits which type of stressors, but do not be limited by what is given in the list since we all handle stress in a unique way.

Overcoming time stress – the best thing to do when experiencing time stress is to make schedule, organize, and prioritize.

Overcoming anticipatory stress – preparation is key. Depending on the upcoming event or activity, it could be helpful to prepare back up plans, practice, ask for feedback and/or help from colleagues/co-workers.

Overcoming situational stress – there is no quick fix, and this might be the most harrowing of all stressors, however, being mindful and improving emotional intelligence can alleviate or reduce situational stress.

Overcoming encounter stress – the best way to reduce this type of stress is to improve self-esteem and through improving social skills.

The third step – be creative, this stress management program can be a guide or a reference in creating your own stress management practices, there are more ways to fight stress such as meditation, finding a hobby, playing/listening to music, games, and all sorts of socially acceptable activities. The key is to explore your options and find the best fit for you.

The fourth step – Test, challenge yourself and try out your chosen coping mechanisms for stress, consider it as a trial-and-error period where you constantly test yourself when experiencing stress.

The fifth step – repetition, one key piece of advice I can give you is that progress is not scaling nor gradual. You can be on top of the mountain today but who knows where you will be tomorrow that is why it is important to keep in mind that when we regress, progress is a process it does not mean that we have gone back to zero it is just an off day, but through repetition of your own practices. You will be able to handle any kind of stress.

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